

The Role of NSS towards Student in Higher Education

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commerce and social science and in the changing scenario these students must be able to support themselves; in spite of the tremendous increase in the number of students undergoing higher education. The entire youth is unable to get education. In the age group of 17 to 24 years only seven per cent youngsters are pursuing higher education.

The maxim, "Higher education for a limited few", has been replaced by Dr Punjabrao Deshmukh movement "Mass education for all homes". According to Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, "The universities should work to impart lofty thoughts to a person and thereby help in building the nation. The universities are symbols of humanitarian, tolerant, logical, progressive and courageous thoughts and search for the truth. Universities should strive uphold the higher goals of the human race".

The nation considers education as a medium to impart the legacy of cultural, social and political values to the coming generation. Dr KV Patayya the learned educationist and writer from Mysore have stated three roles of the university namely learning and teaching, research and extension. Extension is now a compulsory obligation of the university. Being an organization which gives higher education, the university is worked upon as an important agency in this regard. As a part of its social communication activity it has been given the responsibility of extension education and it is expected that education, research and extension activities would be carried out within one roof.

Extension education which is a third objective by UGC according to its new policy of 1976 has been accepted by all

ABSTRACT

The antisocial gap between the educated and uneducated, rich and poor, urban and rural is reduced by bringing together students of all such levels, in the NSS camps. It helps to strength to the spirit national integration. Development of rural India was Mahatma Gandhi's dream. Even after 50 years of independence we cannot say with certainty-which rural India has developed. Illiteracy, Poverty, Superstition, Hygiene, Drinking water, etc., are the various problems still faced by rural population.

Keywords: NSS, Higher Education, Student Behaviour, Self-Discipline, National and Social Responsibilities

INTRODUCTION

21st century is an age of technology. The progress of science and technology has resulted in an outburst of knowledge. Within seconds, news or information of any type can reach any corner of the earth. This has become possible through science and technology. Boundaries of knowledge are ever widening. New openings are being made. It is inevitable that this technology should affect higher education. India has the largest educational system in the world. In the pre - independence period between 1947 and 1950 India had 25 Universities, 200 colleges 1500 teachers and one lakh students. About one per cent persons were taking higher education. Today we have 296 Universities, 13,000 colleges and more than 88 lakh students out of which 83% students, are studying science, universities as a Social obligation and responsibility towards the neglected segment of the society.

True Purpose of Education

- Reestablishment of human principles.
- Character building of students.
- Promotion of abilities to ponder the concentrate.
- Motivation of the students to become progressive and responsible citizens.
- Cultivating a feeling of self-respect in the students and develop their inherent talents. Also to faster in their moral values and spiritual thoughts.
- Creating a feeling of universal brotherhood.
- Developing scientific attitude.

The four pillars of education Delor's report (UNESCO) are:

- Learning to know
- Learning to do
- Learning to live together
- Learning to be

One organization from the European countries has stated the following six principles of education in the 21st century.

- Learning in the 21st century will become the essential part of the everyday human activity.
- Access to learning in the 21st century will need to be as near universal as possible.
- Learning technologies in the 21st century will need to respond flexibly to learner needs.

- Learning supplies in the 21st century will need to adopt new ways to meet the changing demands of their clients and to maximise the potential of new delivery techniques.
- Government in the 21st century will need to play an active role in supporting the learning infrastructure, but should not attempt to control the learning agenda.
- Learning in the 21st century will need to be collaborative enterprise.

The universities must stoutly meet these challenges of the 21st century and then only the lost path to education can be found again.

Objectives of Extension

Extension is an English term. In French it is called Vulgarization and in Encouragement the German it is called berater.

- **Swamsen and Care have defined extension as follows:** "Extension is an educational process, communicating useful information to people, helping them to learn how to use it, to build a better life for themselves, their families and their communities".

Gandhiji visualized the extension of knowledge of the universities to the community. To make his vision true, numerous commissions and experts recommended some kind of service to be rendered by the students to the community and some kind of institutional mechanism to facilitate optimum utilization of education for the welfare of the community.

UGC

UGC is a policy frame on higher education, recognized extension as the third dimension of higher education system, in addition to teaching and research. It declares that of the university system has to discharge adequately its responsibilities is the entire education system and is the society and a whole, it must assume extension as the third important responsibility and give it the same status as research and training. This is a new and extremely significant area which should be developed on the basis of high priority. Extension education tries to develop the Social behaviour of the people, their different groups and the intra and interrelationship of these Social groups. Extension education is a teaching and learning process. It provides an increased amount of useful information and understanding. In general the concept of extension education is used in educating people.

History of NSS

In the pre-independence period it was a dream of Mahatma Gandhi that students should utilize the leisure time available to them during education for service to the nation.

Dr Radhakrishnan, Chairman of University Grants Commission established after independence also expressed his view that in educational institution students should voluntarily do national service. In January 1950, the central advisory committee for education recommended that the students should voluntarily devote some time for physical labour and the teachers should also cooperate in the activity. The central government in 1952 in its first five year plan suggested that the students should devote one year for social work and physical labour.

The then Prime Minister Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru in 1958 instructed the Education Ministry to prepare a useful plan to start National Service in the educational institutions and accordingly on 28th August 1959 under the chairmanship of Dr C D Deshmukh National Service Committee was constituted. The committee suggested that the college students will have to render compulsorily their services to the nation for one year. In 1960 on the instructions of the Central Government Service Scheme of a few countries submitted a report title, "National Services for the Youth". Chairman of the committee Dr. Daulatsingh Kothari (1964-66) recommended that students at all levels should be included in the social service programme. In 1967 in its National educational policy of the Government of India it was decided that work experience and National Service should be made a part of education.

In May 1969 in the joint meeting of the Ministry of Education and UGC it was accepted that National Service could be an effective medium for national integration. Accordingly in the 4th five year plan NSS was accepted as a pilot scheme and was started in a few chosen institutes and universities. On 24th September 1969, the Central Minister for education Dr. VK Rao inaugurated the NSS which was started in 37 universities in India with 40,000 volunteers by coincidence the scheme was started on the birth centenary of Mahatma Gandhi.

Importance of NSS

In addition the knowledge received by the college students, in order to develop their personality through physical labour, service, character and renouncement and to give them an experience of practical life, this programme has distinct role in college and social field. The realisation that my knowledge, my labour, my energy is not for me alone but it is important for you and the entire society, the feeling of "Not me but you" is developed and instead of craving for money, power and selfish motives the young generation is to give lessons of renouncement and service by this programme and hence it is important NSS has a special plan which enables the student to receive information of all components of the society and creates awareness towards his social obligations. The true picture of poverty and leadership of the village life can be seen and experienced by the youth who participate in this activity. This makes their personality more carrying, creative and progressive. Hence I consider this activity entirely valuable.

NSS is an activity through which the university makes a welcome effort to reach the society. We believe that the university should not restrict its work to education and research only, but should also make continual efforts for the progress of the common masses. With this thought the university is implementing numerous activities and NSS is one such important activity.

NSS is not an extra-curricular activity in the true sense. It is an activity to study people and life through active participation in addition it is helpful in the vivid and clear study of various fields of sciences. It is an organised with this view in mind, the college education will receive a new dimension and through the communications and dialogue between the university and the common man, social transformation would be boosted.

NSS has been helpful in making the students aware of the state of the society in our country. It is responsible to a large

extent in moulding the character of the youth and also in cultivating the values of love, compassion and courage in them. The dedication with which the NSS volunteers render service during national calamities is truly commendable.

NSS is an activity of the university which is full of enthusiasm. The university should make it a source of creative future Social reforms. NSS is an auspicious beginning of education in the human religion.

Regular Programmes Conducted by NSS

Various subjects are learned and taught in the college. Through this process the important aim to mould disciplined and dutiful students is to be achieved. Simultaneously they are expected to be aware of the various happening in the social life. To achieve this purpose together with a various educational activities, others programmes are also organised. The idea is to create an all-round awareness in the students and he should be alert about the present situation. In this perspective NSS would be truly useful in student empowerment.

The present educational system is expected to develop the contemplative, mental and intellectual faculties of the student. He much also have practical experience. After leaving the university with a degree he faces many problems and difficulties. If he could have an idea of the difficulties beforehand he would be able to face his future life with courage. It is necessary that he understand the society of which he is a part. If he understands the problems, needs woes, of the society he would truly understand the meaning of life.

Under the NSS basically two types of programmes are conducted. The first type includes the regular activities and the other type is special camps. The objective of both these programmes is to have a direct interaction between the student and the society and to coordinate the efforts of the student for the progress of the society.

The NSS volunteer has to actively participate for 120 hours in a year and this period according to the central NSS regulations is classified as follows:

➤ Volunteer Introduction and Instruction

This is necessary so that the volunteer understands, background, aim, administrative hierarchy, objectives, slogan, NSS symbol, NSS song, NSS day, programmes, activities, camp etc. This information is given during the inaugural ceremony of the NSS and other lectures. For this purpose about 20 hours has to be utilized.

➤ Activities in the Premises

30 hours are to be used for the development and cleanliness of the college in which the volunteer studies. In this period, playground preparation, gardening, surrounding cleanliness, tree plantation and other innovative projects may be included. This requires a well-planned working time table.

➤ Social Work

The Volunteer is expected to devote the remaining 70 hours for social work. This may be made of special camps in adopted village, slum area cleanliness, village development programmes.

Social work may be subdivided as follows:

➤ Work in Associated Organizations

It is necessary to be associated and work with organization serving in the field of child welfare, women welfare, old age homes, institution for the handicapped etc. It is expected that such Work would help is understand the problems of children, women, aged persons and the handicapped and also lend a mental support and entertain them. This would require about 10 hours.

➤ Village Projects and Village Development work

This chiefly includes the work is to be done in and adopted village. This would pertain to removal of illiteracy, water conservation, waste land cultivation, saving fund, agricultural tasks, hygiene, malnutrition, cleanliness, family welfare, education, cooperative movement, road construction, superstition removal, tree plantation and conservation, national integration and unity, Aids awareness etc.

The volunteer should devote 20 hours for this activity.

➤ Urban Projects and Urban

Developmental Activity –

This includes specifically the programmes to be conducted in the urban area. These complete adult education, slum area, Welfare plans, urban defence training, traffic control, basic hygiene centre, help to hospital inmates, help to orphans, environment control, population education, Aids awareness, freedom for addiction, self-employment etc. The volunteers should devote 20 hours for these activities.

➤ Service during National Calamity and National Emergency

Service to the calamity affected people is expected from the NSS volunteers. During times of floods, earthquake, storms, famine the following should be done by the NSS volunteers.

Arrange for help to the calamity affected, resettlement of affected people, procure government aid, and help to the NGO's for distribution of clothing, food and medicine. Arrangement of rallies for donation, collection of relief funds from school, colleges and other institutions, help to government institutions and other such activities. 10 hours should be devoted for the work.

➤ National Day and Celebration

Active participation in National Day celebrations is expected from NSS volunteers. The NSS calendar contains information regarding important days and celebrations. This is done to understand the importance and celebrations and create awareness regarding Youth Day, National Youth Day, Republic Day, Martyr Day, World Understanding Day, Information Day, World Health Day, World Labour Day, World Environment Day, World Population Day, Independence Day, Teachers Day, NSS Day, Gandhiji Birth Day, UNO Day, National Integration Day, Human Rights Day, etc.

About 10 hours should be devoted for this activity in this way the 120 hours of social service with some changes if necessary is to be carried out.

Special Winter Camp

Special winter camp of continuous 10 days should be held in village about 10 km. away from the college. On exceptional cases, if the village is far away but if some innovative project

can be implemented there or if the villagers request for such camp, the same can be conducted with special permission. The camp should be held effectively and aim of the camp should be very clear.

Objectives of the Camp

- To become familiar with the village life.
- To understand the problems and difficulties of the villagers.
- To help and contribute to the development of the village.
- To educate and enlighten the village people regarding subjects like, Indian culture, superstition environment balancing, population, democratic attitude etc.
- Personality development of students through social work.
- To promote respect for labour and self-suffering.
- To convey the information regarding government plans and policies to the people.
- To establish cooperation in between youth, social welfare organizations and the government to prepare new projects.
- To construct roads and water conservation projects.
- To indicate leadership qualities in the youth to prepare local leadership so that it could help implementation of long term projects.
- To cultivate discipline, hygiene values, social alertness in the students.
- To motivate the students and village youth is work in cooperation with the villagers.
- To search the dormant talents in the students, develop their personality and to use their skills in different projects.
- To motivate the students in enthusiastically participate democratically and with cooperation in national integration and nation building.

In addition to the above objectives to implement the specific aims and objectives as decided by the government such as "Youth for eternal development" "Youth for hygiene society" "Youth for tree plantation and conservation" "Youth for national integration and national welfare" are the themes for camps.

There should be close and developmental contacts between the volunteers and people. The students should feel enthusiastic to observe and actively protect natural wealth.

For example: Tree plantation, cleaning the streams and lakes, cleaning the ponds and lakes which are responsible for ill health in villages etc. These activities are expected to be conducted during winter camps. In older days the rishis used to have "Shrama Yadnya" together with "Dnyana Yadnya" nowadays there is no importance given to the "Shrama Yadnya". Those who are more educated feel were shy to perform labour. NSS will help in reducing this shyness towards labour and labour would be looked upon as motivating rather than burdensome.

The antisocial gap between the educated and uneducated, rich and poor, urban and rural is reduced by bringing together students of all such levels, in the NSS camps. It helps to strength to the spirit national integration. Development of rural India was Mahatma Gandhi's dream. Even after 50 years of independence we cannot say with certainty-which rural India has developed. Illiteracy, Poverty, Superstition, Hygiene, Drinking water, etc., are the various problems still faced by rural population.

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